

FI
Facultad de Ingeniería

A C C E S S I B I L I T Y E V A L U A T I O N R E P O R T

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INDEX

01. Introduction
02. Experience
03. Methodology
04. Results
05. Conclusion

INTRODUCCIÓN

This presentation reports on the initial accessibility evaluation conducted by the Instituto de Bioingeniería at the University of Mendoza. Our primary objective was to review the access and data analysis of LSST Data Preview 1 (DP1) through the Rubin Science Platform (RSP) interfaces.

The core goal of this review was to identify specific barriers faced by Blind and Low Vision (BLV) users and to provide preliminary recommendations for immediate and medium-term improvements. This assessment is designed to be the crucial first step in an iterative approach toward full inclusivity.

Road map - Accessibility on astronomy for research (the case of sonoUno)

Courses

1

SONOUNO
DESKTOP
VERSION

2

SONOUNO
WEB
VERSION

3

Southampton
fellowship

REINFORCE

Citizen science project
Real data sonification

4

External
applications

Sensing the Dynamic
Universe
Sonification Workshop
SonoUno-Raspberry-Pi
The Sound of BEARS

5

New Research
lines IBio-UM

6

OAD fellowship

Workshops and courses in Argentina

METHODOLOGY

01. Review of DP1 and RSP interfaces.

Automatic testing of the principal webpage.

Manual testing with screen readers on different platforms.

02. User testing

BLV Spanish natives (navigability through sections)

Group members with English knowledge test some tutorials.

03. Report

Some additional testing with a focus on the API section.

Key challenges and suggestions.

04. Presentation & Q&A Session

Final presentation to CST members.

TODAY

GENERATION OF A NEW ACCOUNT ON THE PLATFORM (RSP)

Identified Barriers and Recommendations

01

Email Verification: The need is understood, but this step can complicate navigation for visually impaired users, as they must find their email application, wait for the message, and refresh the screen until it appears before they can continue.

02

Low Contrast in Video: A minor issue was found in the video tutorial due to low contrast in the red text on a black background.

- The measured contrast ratio is 5.25:1, falling below the WCAG Level AAA standard of 7:1 for normal text.
- **Recommendation:** If the red text color is maintained when the website is in dark mode, it is suggested to add a text box with a white background for messages to improve legibility and reduce eye strain.

GENERATION OF A NEW ACCOUNT ON THE PLATFORM (RSP)

Accessibility Strengths

01

The account creation and login process provides a strong, accessible foundation.

02

The platform utilizes widely adopted authentication methods (such as Google, ORCID, Microsoft, or GitHub), which simplifies the process for users.

03

The tutorial description is detailed and precise.

04

The process was completed successfully using a screen reader, which reproduced all steps without issues.

05

The login experience is considered accessible and consistent with how other widely used platforms handle sign-in.

AUTOMATIC EVALUATION (LIGHTHOUSE)

Performance

Values are estimated and may vary. The [performance score is calculated](#) directly from these metrics. [See calculator.](#)

▲ 0-49 ■ 50-89 ● 90-100

Performance

Values are estimated and may vary. The [performance score is calculated](#) directly from these metrics. [See calculator.](#)

▲ 0-49 ■ 50-89 ● 90-100

Performance

Values are estimated and may vary. The [performance score is calculated](#) directly from these metrics. [See calculator.](#)

▲ 0-49 ■ 50-89 ● 90-100

AUTOMATIC EVALUATION (WAVE)

The screenshot shows the WAVE web accessibility evaluation tool interface. At the top, it displays the WAVE logo and 'powered by WebAIM'. The address bar shows 'https://data.lsst.cloud/'. Below the address bar, there is a 'Styles' toggle switch set to 'ON'. The 'Details' section is active, showing a summary of issues: 3 Errors, 0 Contrast Errors, 5 Alerts, 4 Features, 10 Structure, and 4 ARIA. An AIM Score of 8.1 out of 10 is displayed with a green progress bar. Below the summary, there are sections for '3 Errors' (3 X Missing alternative text) and '5 Alerts' (2 X Redundant alternative text, 3 X Noscript element).

The screenshot shows the 'Order' tab in the WAVE tool. The tab is selected, and the content area displays instructions: 'Order, role, and accessible name (what is read by a screen reader) for all navigable page elements are listed. Elements that do not have a function should not be listed.' Below the instructions, a list of links is shown, numbered 1 through 9: 1 Link: Homepage of Rubin Science Platform, 2 Link: Portal, 3 Link: Notebooks, 4 Link: APIs, 5 Link: Documentation, 6 Link: Support, 7 Link: Community, 8 Link: Log in, and 9 Link: Preview.

The screenshot shows the 'Contrast' tab in the WAVE tool. The tab is selected, and the content area displays a message: 'No contrast errors were detected in the page. Manual testing is necessary to test for other potential contrast issues.' Below the message, there are two color pickers: 'Foreground' with a hex value of #0000FF and 'Background' with a hex value of #FFFFFF. The 'Contrast Ratio' is shown as 8.59:1. The 'Text Size' is Normal. Below the text size, there is a 'Sample' button. At the bottom, it states 'WCAG AA: Pass' and 'WCAG AAA: Pass'. A note at the bottom says 'WAVE does not detect contrast errors when gradients, filters, or background transparency are present. WCAG requires a conformant'.

Informes completos: https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1_k_wp0dGlxJcttcNRxawg19GxxilykGN?usp=sharing

GENERAL DOCUMENTATION

Critical Barriers

01

Usability Disruption (Loss of Context): This is identified as a major usability issue and a key barrier that must be prioritized for remediation.

- When a user follows a link and then navigates back, they often experience a loss of their reading context because the cursor is placed at the beginning of the page. This forces users to restart at the top of the webpage or manually search for their prior reading position, which significantly disrupts focus and workflow.

02

Broken Links: Minor issues include the presence of broken links (detailed on the report).

GENERAL DOCUMENTATION

Strengths and Accessibility

01

Good Screen Reader Navigation: The general documentation has a simple layout, describes all expected topics, and allows for good navigation with screen readers.

02

Consistent Structure: The interface across different documentation pages is consistent, with element groups remaining in the same place.

03

Non-Disruptive Elements: Navigation elements (such as top, right-side, and end-of-page menus) are included and do not interrupt navigation with the screen reader.

PLATFORM SECTIONS - OVERVIEW

Three Data Access Methods

The Rubin Science Platform (RSP) offers users three distinct methods for accessing data from the start: **1. Portal** (database interface using multiple fields); **2. Notebooks** (interactive data analysis environment); **3. API** (access via command line or third-party applications).

- Each format adds versatility, allowing researchers to use the method that best suits their needs.
- Overall, the Notebooks aspect and the PyVO connection are highlighted as the most accessible options.
- While the Portal format presents accessibility challenges, its inclusion maintains consistency with existing astronomical databases.

PLATFORM SECTIONS - PORTAL

Description and Usability

- The Portal format displays data using multiple fields and queries, which is a common approach in most astronomical databases.
- This approach is considered an acceptable practice because the majority of users can access the data, and two other, more accessible methods are available.

Cognitive Barrier

- The Portal tool is considered less accessible compared to the others.
- The limitation stems from the high cognitive load imposed on Blind and Low Vision (BLV) users by the sheer quantity of fields and queries displayed on the screen.
- Tutorials are considered adequate and detailed, aiding recognition tasks to help users become familiar with element locations.

PLATFORM SECTIONS - NOTEBOOKS

Screen Reader Barrier

- **Improvement Needed:** The NVDA screen reader does not detect the "Small" and "Large" server options as clickable buttons on the first screen.
- **Recommendation:** It is suggested to potentially change these elements to checkboxes to ensure screen readers correctly detect their function.

Server Options

Image	Options
<input checked="" type="radio"/> Recommended (Release r29.2.0, RSP Build 2244) <input type="radio"/> Release r29.2.1 (RSP Build 2332) <input type="radio"/> Weekly 2025_43 <input type="radio"/> Weekly 2025_42 <input type="radio"/> Daily 2025_10_26 <input type="radio"/> Daily 2025_10_25 <input type="radio"/> Daily 2025_10_24 <input type="radio"/> Select uncached image (slower start): Recommended (Release r29.2.0, RSP Build 2244) ▼	<input type="radio"/> Small (1.0 CPU, 4Gi RAM) <input checked="" type="radio"/> Large (4.0 CPU, 16Gi RAM) <input type="checkbox"/> Enable debug logs <input type="checkbox"/> Reset user environment: relocate .cache, .conda, .config, .eups, jupyter, .local, and .user_setups

Start

PLATFORM SECTIONS - NOTEBOOKS

High Accessibility and Features

- The Notebook format is increasingly used for data analysis and offers **significant improvements in accessibility and navigation** for screen reader users.
- It is highlighted as one of the **most accessible data access methods**.
- **Multilingual Support:** A key benefit is the feature in the introductory sections that allows content to be displayed in **Spanish**, enhancing accessibility for non-English speakers.
- **Strong Content:** Initial steps are well-explained, and the system effectively integrates documentation for the utilized libraries, providing a valuable resource.
- **Robust Performance:** Code executed rapidly and consistently, showing efficient performance even in complex analyses.

PLATFORM SECTIONS - APIS (TOKEN AND GENERAL CHALLENGES)

Purpose and Access

The API format adds versatility by allowing researchers to access data using third-party applications or the command line. The documentation describes two main access options: TOPCAT and PyVO.

Significant Authentication Barrier

- **Token Generation Difficulty:** The process to generate the User Token is challenging, requiring users to copy a key from a pop-up window, save it, and re-access it.
- **Screen Reader Omission:** During the challenging token generation process, the NVDA screen reader on Windows omits critical text between “Create” and “somewhere secure on your local system”.
- **Poor Error Handling:** When attempting to create a user token without entering a name, **no error is displayed**, and the window stays static, giving the impression that the system is frozen.

PLATFORM SECTIONS - APIS

TOPCAT (Java Application)

01

Major Barrier: TOPCAT does not allow its components to be read by screen readers like Orca.

02

It utilizes several **pop-up windows** that complicate the login process.

03

The tool is considered difficult for visually impaired people to use.

PLATFORM SECTIONS - APIS

PyVO (Command Line / Python)

01

Accessibility Strength: PyVO, which is related to the astropy package, is intuitive and can be used from the command line. It is highlighted as one of the most accessible methods.

02

Documentation Gap: A specific tutorial for establishing the connection using a Token was not found in the main PyVO documentation.

03

Successful Use: Once the correct external code was obtained to establish the connection, database queries were performed without problems using Python and PyVO from the command line.

NOTEBOOK AND PYVO

Access for BLV users

An important detail to consider, especially for BLV people, is that while data access is generally achieved effectively, they can only access numerical data.

In the case of Notebooks and PyVO, the strength is that a table sonification package like STRAUSS or sonoUno can be used. For the latter, including a tutorial would be very useful.

In addition, if the table could be downloaded, other sonification software could be used.

CATEGORIZED ACCESSIBILITY FINDINGS (RSP & DP1)

Critical Barrier

These issues represent significant obstacles to access that severely hinder usability for the target community and must be prioritized for remediation.

- **Language Barrier:** Most information is presented in English, making the platform inaccessible for non-English speakers. (Remediation includes leveraging existing Spanish capabilities and expanding multilingual support across the entire platform's user-facing documentation).
- **Tutorials to use table sonification:** This feature can significantly enhance the recognition of data tables and grant autonomy to visually impaired individuals, allowing them to interpret a graph independently without relying on the intervention of another person.

CATEGORIZED ACCESSIBILITY FINDINGS (RSP & DP1)

Moderate Barriers

These represent major usability issues or specific technical failures that disrupt workflow and require timely attention.

- **Usability Disruption (Loss of Context):** A major usability issue found in the general documentation (e.g., Firefly documentation) is the loss of the user's reading context upon returning from a link. Users are forced to restart at the top of the page, significantly disrupting focus and workflow. This issue must be prioritized for remediation.
- **API Screen Reader Omission:** During the challenging token generation process, critical text is omitted by the NVDA screen reader on Windows. (This omission is considered moderate because the missing information is not critical for understanding the token tutorial).

CATEGORIZED ACCESSIBILITY FINDINGS (RSP & DP1)

Low Barriers

These issues affect specific functionalities or segments of the platform, and while important, are mitigated by the presence of more accessible alternatives.

- **Cognitive Load in Portal:** The Portal tool is less accessible due to the high cognitive load imposed on Blind and Low Vision (BLV) users by the sheer quantity of fields and queries displayed. (This is considered a low barrier because two other, more accessible access methods are available).
- **TOPCAT Incompatibility:** The TOPCAT program, coded in Java, does not allow its components to be read by screen readers (like Orca), making it a difficult tool for visually impaired people to use. (This is considered a low barrier because the PyVO option is available and more accessible).
- **Low Contrast & Broken Links:** Minor issues include a low contrast ratio (5.25:1) in the video tutorial's red-on-black text (falling below WCAG Level AAA standards), and the presence of broken links within the documentation (e.g., the IRSA Workspace webpage 404 error and the 'Roman documentation' link).

C O N C L U S I O N

The initial evaluation confirms that the Rubin Science Platform (RSP) provides a **strong, accessible foundation** in its core services, particularly regarding account creation and login. Of the three access methods, the **Notebooks** aspect and the **PyVO** connection are highlighted as the most accessible options.

This evaluation is the critical first step in an iterative approach toward full inclusivity, ensuring the platform meets the needs of the target community.

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THANKS

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